

Development of Functional Clothing for Sensory Sensitivities of Children with Autism Spectrum Disorder

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Abstract:

Clothing is especially significant to children with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) because it not only helps them to feel independent, secure, and comfortable but also decreases the difficulty of using components of dressing, like buttons, zippers, etc. Due to the delay in developing motor abilities, caregivers of autistic children must aid their children in dressing. Most children with ASD have sensory difficulties, and some clothing attributes like texture, seams, and tags can heighten their sensitivities. The study aimed to design functional clothing for children with ASD tailored to their specific needs of reducing sensory sensitivities and stimming behavior. The objective was also to identify and incorporate clothing components that affect motor limitations, psychological concerns, and social demands. The current study involved children from two special schools for ASD. The methodology used a descriptive and exploratory research approach to gather information on clothing requirements, color and texture preferences, and factors that influence sensory sensitivities and stimming behavior in children with ASD. Data was collected through in-depth semi-structured and structured interviews with caregivers, occupational, and speech therapists, respectively; informal interviews with children with ASD substantiated by detailed observation of their individual and group behavior. After content analysis, a selection of tops and bottoms was constructed for pilot testing on individuals to assess the wearability, utility, and aesthetics of the clothes. Based on the test results, the final range was created with structural and applied design features appropriate for children with ASD that can address the issues of sensory sensitivities and stimming behavior.

Keywords: *Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), functional clothing, motor skills, sensory processing, social need*

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1. Introduction

Clothes represent one of the necessities for human existence [1]. Humans are satisfied when their clothes meet a range of needs. Fashion designer Michael Kors famously said, "Clothes are like a good meal, a good movie, and a good piece of music." This comment perfectly demonstrates how clothes are intrinsically connected to our identities on a psychological as well as a physical level [2]. Children's attire is usually more casual than adult wear. Children should wear comfortable clothing with protective characteristics appropriate for their activities because they are very active and energetic ^[1]. Children with autism may have certain preferences or sensitivities regarding apparel. It is critical to recognize and respect these unique children's preferences to ensure that they feel at ease and comfortable.

Autistic children have certain preferences and sensitivities regarding clothes, such as materials and textures, seamless and tag-less designs, and adaptable clothing options [3]. Adaptive clothing can enhance the comfort and overall well-being of children with autism by considering their clothing preferences and issues related to sensory processing. Children with autism frequently struggle with sensory processing dysfunction. As a result, they could be sensitive to certain fabrics, colors, or patterns. It might be difficult to find clothing that is stylish, comfortable, and functional for those with autism.

Children with autism may experience clothing as harsh or stiff, particularly if they have heightened sensory sensitivities. For some, even minor irritants such as tags and seams can be problematic, leading to discomfort or skin irritation. Given the spectrum of sensory experiences, individuals with hyper-sensitivity may find such features particularly distressing. Therefore, for those with autism, it is crucial to use clothing that is soft and free from potentially bothersome seams or tags, to ensure comfort and minimize irritation [4].

A neurological and developmental condition, ASD affects a person's behavior, ability to learn, and social relationships [5]. Autism Spectrum Disorder affects a person's perceptions and interactions with others, which can cause difficulties with social interaction and communication. The disorder is also associated with limited and recurring behavioral patterns/stimming behavior [6].

The term "spectrum" refers to the wide range of symptoms and severity levels associated with autism spectrum disorder [7, 8]. ASD can affect a person for their entire life, even though it often develops initially in early childhood [9, 10]. Autism may become apparent in early childhood, but the condition is frequently not diagnosed until much later [11]. Even though autism can be diagnosed at any age, it is classified as a "developmental disorder". This is because most symptoms appear within the first two years of life [5]. This number rises to 1 in 125 among children aged 2 to 6 across five states in north and west India, and 1 in 80 among children aged 6 to 9 [12]. ASD is a broad category that includes a variety of challenges that are characterized by varying degrees of difficulty in social engagement and communication. Additional features include unusual activities and behavior patterns, such as difficulties transitioning between activities, attention to detail, and unique responses to sensations. People with autism frequently co-occur with emotional and behavioral disorders (EBPs), such as sadness, anxiety, hyperactivity and inattention, violent behaviors, and difficulties sleeping or self-harm [11, 13 & 14]. When developing and implementing interventions for individuals with autism and other developmental disabilities, their perspectives must be considered. Community and social activities must be combined with care to improve accessibility, inclusivity, and support [11]. Autism affects daily functioning in a variety of ways. The impact of autism on daily life can vary greatly depending on the unique challenges and strengths of each individual. By identifying and addressing these problems, one can assist individuals with autism in leading happy, meaningful lives. Regardless of a person's neurodiversity, one may create a more accepting and inclusive society by raising awareness, empathetic responses, and supportive measures [15].

1.1 Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD)

It is a neuro-developmental disorder marked by persistent difficulties with speech, nonverbal communication, social interaction, and repetitive/restrictive behavior [16, 17 & 18]. It has an impact on the neurological system in addition to the person's overall health - mental, emotional, physical, and social. Unfavorable prenatal, perinatal, and neonatal circumstances, such as advanced maternal age and birth before 32 weeks of gestation, are connected to an increased risk of ASD. The prevalence of ASD, which is currently estimated to be between 1% and 2% worldwide, has increased in recent years as awareness has expanded and diagnostics have improved [19]. Being autistic does not mean that a person is ill or suffers from a particular condition; rather, it simply means that their brain processes differently than other individuals. The National Autistic Society states that although autism cannot be cured, it can be improved. Autism is a developmental disability that affects people throughout their lives [20].

1.2 Areas of Development affected by ASD are as follows

- ***Social Awareness and Interaction***
Autism spectrum disorders are characterized by differences in language, understanding, and communication abilities. They have a unique perspective when interacting with others. This results in differences in the way the person interacts with people and builds relationships.
- ***Integration and Processing of Sensations***
Sensory changes can impact not only the eight senses of sight, hearing, touch, taste, and smell, but also vestibular (balance), proprioception (body awareness), and interoception (internal sensations). These variances will vary from person to person, and a variety of factors, such as the surroundings or the time of day, may affect how receptive they are.
- ***Thinking Flexibly, Processing Information and Interpreting***

There are differences in the attention span, interests, and learning styles of people with autism. One method to do this is to be deeply committed to a certain activity. They usually feel safer and more at ease with regularity and structure since it lessens uncertainty, as they are not as adaptive as others. Although individuals with autism spectrum disorders are not alike, there are some traits that they share. A person diagnosed with autism spectrum disorder may have behavioral and social difficulties like making eye contact, asking meaningful questions about their interests, initiating, or continuing a conversation, reacting to people appropriately, and using facial expressions suited for the situation, understanding the perspective of others. The individual may also exhibit behaviors like withdrawing from other people; engaging in repeated or stimming activities like rocking back and forth or repeating words; becoming very interested in a specific topic; or finding it difficult to adapt to changes in their environment or daily schedule, varying from neurotypical people in terms of sensitivity to sensory input, such as loud noises, finding it difficult to go asleep.

A person's balance, coordination, and motor abilities can occasionally be affected by autism [21]. Though all autistic people have certain characteristics in common; they are all different because autism is considered a spectrum disorder. The autism spectrum is not a linear range that runs from high to low; rather, it is a spectrum that encompasses all possible differences between people [22].

1.3 ASD can be classified into three levels

Level 1: Needs assistance

A Level 1 person may have social challenges that necessitate help.

They might find it difficult to start discussions with strangers, behave in a way that other people would expect, and stay involved in the conversation. As a result, making friends can be difficult, especially without the right support. In addition, the person may feel uncomfortable in unfamiliar or shifting situations, need help with planning and organizing, or feel compelled to follow rigid behavioral standards.

Level 2: Necessitates significant assistance

Compared to level 1, level 2 individuals need more help.

The person may have trouble speaking effectively even with assistance, and they are more prone to respond in ways that may surprise or be unacceptable for neurotypical people. They may be very wordy, restrict their conversation to highly specific topics, and struggle to read or understand nonverbal signs like facial expressions. One of their actions could be to turn away from the person they are speaking to. It can also be difficult for people with level 2 autism to go about their daily lives since they struggle with change adjustment. When faced with change, they could experience an immense amount of pain.

Level 3: Necessitates extremely strong assistance

Level 3 autism needs the most assistance. They may avoid or restrict social connection, find it difficult to play with friends, show little interest in friends, and find it difficult to form new ones. Both verbal and nonverbal communication will be very difficult for them to utilize or understand. They may find it difficult to change their routines or activities, engage in repetitive actions (such as flipping objects) to the point where it interferes with their ability to function, and become quite agitated if they must shift their focus or job [21].

1.4 The brain of ASD individuals and Sensory disorders

Several changes in the brain have been identified in individuals diagnosed with autism. The brain's overall size as well as the characteristics and skills of different brain regions can vary [23]. One of the earliest indicators of abnormal brain growth during ASD development is head circumference measurements in newborns and early children with autism [9].

The brain's **cerebellum** is a small, spherical area that sits behind the cerebral cortex. It regulates certain cognitive functions like language, attention, balance, and mobility. Large, abnormal cerebella are commonly seen in people with autism. Along with difficulties with cognition, social connection, and communication, these abnormalities may lead to problems with balance, coordination, and motor abilities [23, 24].

A smaller **amygdala** in autistic individuals may be associated with increased levels of anxiety and terror. This may contribute to the understanding of why certain autistic people avoid social situations or become quite upset when

their routines are disturbed [23, 25]. The **cortex** lies in the outermost layer of the brain and is involved in higher-order thinking skills such as planning and decision-making. It is also responsible for processing data from the body's sensory organs, such as sight, hearing, and touch [23, 26]. People with autism usually have thicker cortical layers than people without autism. This discrepancy may help to explain why social interaction and communication are often difficult for people with autism. The thicker brain may also be connected to autism's repetitive/stimming behavior and limited interests [23].

To make decisions on how to react to sensory input, the brain can access information stored in memory [27]. Sensory processing is the capacity to process and respond to sensory input. To process information, the body makes use of the following eight sensory systems: Visual (sight), Auditory (sound), Gustatory (taste), Olfactory (smell), Tactile (touch) Interoception (internal sensors for physiological conditions), Proprioceptive (input from muscles and joints), and Vestibular (balance) [28, 29]. Many children with autism do not process information in the same ways as their typically developing peers. Participation problems can arise when a person's sensory processing pattern and their environment do not align and they may exhibit variations in their sensory processing, such as hyperresponsivity (more sensitivity) or hypo-responsivity (lower sensitivity) to specific environmental signals [30, 31].

Color is one of the elements that probably influence human psychology greatly; this is especially true when attempting to comprehend how people with ASD perceive things. According to some studies, color significantly affects children's visual stress. The study by Paron-Wildes, 2005, discovered that 85% of children with ASD had more vivid color vision than typical children and that they are aroused by environments that are vibrant with color. People with autism suffer psychological effects from color because of their sensitivity to it. Soft hues are generally calming and bright colors fascinating to people with autism [20, 32].

Touch sensitivity is a common concern among people with sensory processing disorders, regardless of age. Occupational therapists who have received training in sensory integration would commonly label this issue with touch perception as "tactile defensiveness", "over-responsivity to touch" or "touch sensitivity" [33]. The brain filters out a lot of moderate sensory stimuli, such as touch, background noise, and the sensation of clothing against our skin and a person usually continues without any difficulty or second thought. In the case of individuals with tactile defensiveness, there is no filter. These so-called "non-threatening sensations" turn into a serious problem that can cause tension and worry, making it difficult for them to perform regular tasks [34].

Self-stimulatory behaviors such as repetitive motions or noises are referred to as stimming [35] which could be a whole-body or an isolated stimming activity. Sometimes these activities might be distracting and get in the way of learning or work [34]. Under some conditions, they can be disturbing and interfere with emotional self-control [35].

Children with ASD are more likely than typically developing children to have delays in both the gross and fine motor skills [16]. Poor balance, aberrant posture during movements, and coordination problems with both gross and fine motor abilities can be some of the challenges [36]. According to test findings (Movement Assessment Battery for Children 2 (M-ABC2) and Test of Gross Motor Development-2 (TGMD-2)), children aged 3 to 16 claimed that up to 80% of them had a definite impairment in their overall motor skills; similarly, 80% of children with an ASD diagnosis also reported having gross motor delay [16].

When faced with challenges and problems, people with autism can draw strength from their various abilities. Autism does not make someone less than or discourage them from doing anything. They may demonstrate different points of view in response to questions, a strong eye for detail, or a preference for topics that bring them joy [22].

Like all people, for children with autism, clothes have a significant impact on their everyday lives. It is a basic physiological and psychological need because it provides comfort and protection from undesirable outside effects [3]. The ability to be independent, secure, and comfortable while minimizing the difficult components of dressing, such as buttons, zippers, and closing openings, makes clothes even more critical in determining the quality of life for children with autism.

Based on the observations and data gathered from the sources, parents, and caregivers of children with autism must assist their children with dressing. 90% of children with autism, experience sensory difficulties, i.e., they either avoid or become anxious about certain sounds, textures, or smells [20].

Children with autism spectrum disorders frequently experience difficulties with their motor abilities, especially when it comes to dressing themselves [20]. In the current paper, this issue has been thoroughly addressed by including self-help features that allow children with ASD to dress up with psychological and physical comfort.

1.5 Common Clothing Sensitivities among Autistic Individuals

For individuals with autism, some garment components may trigger sensitivity. Each person may have varying levels of sensitivity hence it is important to highlight the key factors that affect their comfort, sensory needs, and overall well-being.

a) Understanding Sensory Sensitivities

- **Hyper or Hyposensitivity:** Children with ASD may be extremely sensitive to certain textures, seams, or tags in clothing.
- **Textures:** Soft, seamless, and tag-less clothing is often preferred. Natural fibers like cotton are breathable, absorb moisture, and can be more comfortable than synthetic materials.
- **Avoiding Irritation:** Clothing should avoid tight fits, rough fabrics, or labels that might cause discomfort or distractions.

b) Ease of Dressing/ Self-Help Garments

- **Simple Fastenings:** Elastic waistbands, large buttons, magnetic fasteners, etc., can help children dress independently.
- **Adaptability:** Clothes should be easy to put on and take off, especially for children who struggle with fine motor skills.
- **Elastic and Adjustable:** Consider clothing that can be self-reliant, such as elastic and adjustable waistbands.

c) Safety Considerations

- **Non-toxic Materials:** Clothing should be made from materials that are safe and free from harmful chemicals, as children with ASD might have heightened sensitivities.
- **Avoidance of Hazards:** No loose strings or cords that could pose strangulation risk, especially for younger children.

d) Comfort and Movement

- **Flexible Fabrics:** Clothing should allow for a full range of motion, as many children with ASD benefit from physical activity.
- **Layering Options:** Provide the ability to add or remove layers easily, as children with ASD might have difficulty regulating their body temperature.

e) Clothing Options

- **Compression Clothing:** Some children with ASD find comfort in wearing compression garments, which can have a calming effect.
- **Control of Temperature:** Individuals with ASD may have difficulties regulating their body temperature due to differences in sensory processing, autonomic function, sweating responses, and difficulty in communicating discomfort, which makes them more vulnerable to clothing that traps heat or restricts airflow. Comfort could be improved by using breathable, moisture-absorbing, and moisture-wicking fabrics [37].

f) Style and Social Considerations

- **Age-appropriate Fashion:** Ensuring that clothing is not only comfortable but also aligned with the child's age and social context can help them feel more included in peer group and society.
- **Avoid Over-stimulation:** Choose clothing with simple designs and patterns to avoid overwhelming children who may be sensitive to visual stimuli.

2. Significance of the study

The project intends to develop clothing that is adaptive and functional keeping sensory sensitivity, stimming behavior, and ease of dressing with self-help features as essential factors of consideration. Functional apparel is designed to improve the quality of life for children with autism, whose skills and gross and fine motor skills

development are different from those of children with typical development. Children with ASD also experience clothing sensitivity hence, the creation of clothing that is specifically customized to meet their needs is essential. Throughout the design process, consideration is given to social needs, psychological aspects, and physical limitations. For children with ASD, the clothing should be simple to put on, cozy, secure, and incorporate self-reliant elements. The clothing developed is expected to have psychological advantages in addition to aiding in improved sensory and social integration with society.

3. Objectives of the study

1. To identify the clothing needs and challenges experienced while dressing by children with ASD
2. To understand the sensory sensitivities concerning clothing in children with ASD.
3. To understand the aspects that influence stimming behavior in children with ASD
4. To develop a range of clothing that is suitable to provide comfort from sensory sensitivities and stimming behavior.

4. Materials and Methods

To learn more about the clothing requirements, preferred colors and textures, and variables influencing stimming activity in children with ASD, the study used an exploratory and descriptive research methodology. Close observation of the children's individual and group behaviors, as well as in-depth semi-structured and structured interviews, were used to collect data. To evaluate the wearability, usefulness, and aesthetics of the clothing, a range of top and bottom wear was made following content analysis and used in subject pilot testing. With structural and applied design appropriate for children with ASD, a final range was created based on the test results.

Area Selection: Two special schools for autistic children were chosen as the research locations.

Sample selection: Five occupational therapists, three speech therapists, seven special educators and caregivers, and 30 autistic children in the age range of 6-10 years old comprise the sample.

Tools of Data collection included in-person observations, expert opinions, a sample of autistic children, and extensive semi-structured and structured interviews with therapists (occupational therapists, speech therapists), special educators, and caregivers.

Personal interviews were done for the research project involving occupational therapists, speech therapists, special educators, and caretakers. Additionally, observational, and experimental studies on preferred textures, colours, and designs were carried out with children who have ASD. To do this, a sample of 30 children, comprising 10 from level I, 12 from level II, and 8 from level III ASD, were chosen using purposive sampling techniques. Children with ASD completed three different kinds of tasks: one involving fabric texture, while the other two involved color preferences and motor development.

The activities were carried out under the direction and supervision of qualified occupational therapists and special educators.

5. Results & Discussion

The study was carried out to analyze the clothing-related challenges faced by children with ASD. The content analysis of the interviews and observations provided data on the clothing needs of children with ASD, fabric, and color preferences, and sensory and motor developmental deficiencies that impact their daily life.

The factors that affect the sensory behavior were categorized [Table 1 and 2] and the results provide directions for modifications that can be implemented in the garments made for children with autism.

Table 1 – Distribution of the respondents according to their preferred clothing attributes (n=30)

Sr. No.	Attribute	Category	No. of Respondent	%
1.	Fabric/Textile function	Denim	10	33.33
		Corduroy	07	23.33
		Knit	07	23.33
		Rubber print	01	3.33
		Felt	02	6.66
		Un-cut pile	03	10
2.	Colour	Blur	09	30
		Green	07	23.33
		Red	01	3.33
		Yellow	03	10
		White	02	6.66
		Black	01	3.33
		Pink	07	23.33

Table 2 – Analysis of clothing needs for autistic children and their implementation methods

Requirements of design implementations	Findings	General aspect in context to children with ASD	Observation	Design implementation
Standard criteria for creating collections for individuals with special needs.	Delayed motor development	Physical attribute	Gap analysis-Lack of availability of special clothing for ASD children	Functional & aesthetic garments with features added as per the requirements of ASD children
Design modification based on the needs of children with ASD	Slow mind and academic growth due to brain development	Psychological	Difficulties in wearability	Easy to wear clothing with self-help features
Latest garment design collection for kids	Fashion trends for children wear	Design	No specific implementation for sensory difficulties	Including sensory integration details in garments
Suitable fabric	Fabric and material theory	Material	No specific material being used based on ASD requirements	Comfortable & breathable material to enhance ASD children's activities
Clothing with a multipurpose design concept	Functional features	Functional	Limited functionality in clothing for ASD children	Incorporation of functional features
Color implementation	Color theory	Color	No color specification with regards to the children with ASD	Specific colors used based on ASD children's preferences

Table 1 reveals that children's preferences for cool and smooth denim were 33%, followed by 23% for knit and corduroy and 30% of children liked blue and 23.33% favored pink and green.

Table 2 shows the analysis of the gap between market-available clothes and the needs of children with ASD. The dressing-related issues faced can be resolved by considering the needs and requirements of children with ASD like using cotton-based fabrics, preferred colors, seamless construction, minimal trims, no tags, elastic waistbands, magnetic fasteners, and zippers in place of buttons, flexible front and back garments and smart opening methods keeping in mind the sensory sensitivities which are described in greater depth below.

5.1 Clothing requirements

Children with ASD have unique physiological and psychological needs that influence their clothing preferences, some key considerations are sensory sensitivities from fabric and color, stimming behavior, motor development, safety, temperature regulation, and ease of use.

Sensory issues with clothes can be problematic for children who are uncomfortable wearing certain types of clothing due to their sensory sensitivities [38]. Developing independence and confidence in dressing skills through suitable approaches and techniques can improve the daily routine and quality of life for children with ASD. The features added were easy-to-wear clothing such as pull-on/elasticated bottoms, flexible front, and back bottoms because they get confused between front and back, garments without labels and tags (printed labels), and clothing with flat seams, which are ideal for all three levels of autism [Fig. 1].

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Figure 1: #Style 1 for Age Group 6-10 years

Fabric

Many individuals with autism have unique anticipation in response to touch, certain clothing items, or labels and tags on clothing. People with autism experience anxiety and distress when they come across certain unpleasant stimuli, or undesirable textures in their environment [39, 40]. Depending on their texture, fabrics can be either calming or aggravating. This ability is simply enhanced for many individuals and children who have higher sensitivity and ASD [41]. It has been observed that children with autism tend to feel happy and comfortable when they are wearing smooth and soft fabrics [Table 1].

An experimental study comprising of 30 children from all three ASD levels i.e. 10 from level I, 12 from level II, and 8 from level III—was carried out for this research. Different fabrics including knits, uncut pile textiles, fur, felt, velvet, denim, and corduroy, were introduced to each child. A greater inclination for knits, corduroy, and denim was

indicated by 80% of children across all three levels [Fig. 2]. Additionally, since fur fabric can cause children to become distracted from their work and engage in stimming behavior, instructors do not recommend it.

Figure 2: Fabric preferences by children with autism of level II and III

Figure 3: Color preferences by children with autism of level I, II and III

Breathability

Sensory sensitivity is common in people with autism spectrum disorder (ASD), which may interfere with their ability to regulate body temperature [42, 43]. Therefore, this element was taken into consideration when choosing the materials, and no interlinings were used in the development of the clothing. Cotton-based materials were utilized like cotton-based knit fabric, as preferred by all 3 levels of children with features such as softness, stretchability, air permeability, and wrinkle and tear resistance. Denim is durable and strong, whereas corduroy's thick weave makes it resistant to wear and tear, and the ribbed structure hides stains and other flaws. Depending on the thickness, these three textiles are suitable for both summer and winter use.

Touch Sensitivity

Children with autism are not comfortable with rough textures, so they are introduced to new textures at an early age (6-8 years) to get familiarized. As a result, touch sensitivity develops earlier than later in life. Textures in the form of applique (using felt, uncut pile, etc.), patchwork, and embroidery were used in the garments to develop touch sensitivity [Fig. 4].

Figure 4: Different Textures to develop touch sensitivity

Color

As discussed, children with ASD see colors more intensely than other children and are aroused by color-rich environments. People with autism suffer psychological effects because of their color sensitivity. Bright colors fascinate people with autism, whereas soft colors calm them.

The same sample of ASD children was used for the color activity. In this exercise, thumb and hand impressions were obtained to determine color preferences and fine motor skills. They were introduced to a variety of warm, cool, and bright colors, including blue, green, red, yellow, white, black, and pink. The results from all three levels reveal that 30% of children liked blue and 23.33% favored pink and green [Fig. 3].

5.2 Stimming Behavior

Under some conditions, children with ASD may stim. Stimming itself does not always provide an issue; it only does so when it interferes with learning, isolates a person from society, or becomes harmful [35].

Changes have been made to the clothes for children with ASD to decrease stimming behavior. The rib knit structure has been employed in place of woven cuffs and collars, which is an ideal feature for all three levels of autism.

According to the data collected, cuffs, collars, strings, etc., are reported to activate the stimming activity. Typically, the length of ribs is two inches; however, to decrease stimming activity and give soft compression at the wrist and ankle areas, three inches of ribs were provided for children with ASD. Furthermore, as previously mentioned, stimming behavior also affects the vestibular (balance) sensory system of the body. To prevent potentially dangerous scenarios, knee and elbow paddings have been incorporated into the clothing, which is an ideal feature, particularly for level 3 children with ASD and for children in the age range of 6 to 8 years who require additional protection from falls in their clothing [Fig. 5 & Fig. 6].

Figure 5: #Style 2 for Age Group 6-10 years

Figure 6: #Style 3 for Age Group 6-10

5.3 Motor Development

Easy-to-wear clothing with pull-on bottoms and zipper openings is well-suited for children with all three levels of ASD, while for level 3 children, magnetic buttons can be considered. These modifications were made in consideration of the motor development delays observed in children with ASD. To enhance fine motor skills and build self-reliance in children aged 8-10 years, button openings were incorporated in certain cases [Fig.7 & Fig. 8].

Figure 7: #Style 4 for Age Group 10-12 years

Figure 8: #Style 5 for Age Group 10-12 years

8. Conclusion

Children with autism spectrum disorder have a variety of symptoms, but the majority exhibit sensory processing issues, particularly when it comes to clothing. Their unique apparel design requirements are critical to their social presence and quality of life. Autistic children have special needs. When developing clothing for children with autism, the current research focused on developing garments that were more functional and aesthetic, so fashion characteristics are embedded in clothing too. The emphasis was on bridging the gap between the limitations in the available apparel and the clothing requirements mentioned by caregivers, therapists, and children with autism. The criteria covered aspects such as safety, functionality, comfort, psychological, social, and aesthetics. The content analysis of interviews and observations with therapists, caregivers, special educators, and children with ASD resulted in a list of clothing requirements and issues that children with autism confront daily.

To meet the special needs of children with ASD, the range developed includes a set of upper and bottom garments designed with careful consideration of sensory sensitivities, ease of dressing, and comfort and movement. Fabrics

such as cotton-based knits, denim, and corduroy were chosen for their softness and flexibility, while functional features like pull-on designs and flexible front-back bottoms enhance the ease of dressing. Safety considerations were addressed through the incorporation of padding and ribbing in place of cuffs and collars, reducing discomfort and potential hazards. Additionally, the inclusion of style and social considerations, such as applique work, patchwork, and embroideries, ensures that the clothing not only meets practical needs but also supports the child's social presence and self-expression. This comprehensive approach aimed to improve the overall experience of wearing clothing for children with autism, enhancing their quality of life and facilitating their social interactions.

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